

UCD SCHOOL OF ARCHAEOLOGY

ARCH10150

Anthropology: An Introduction

Syllabus

Module Coordinator

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MODULE OUTLINE

This module provides an introduction to the discipline of anthropology—the study of humans and human diversity in the present and the past. Anthropology examines the diversity of human societies and cultures across space and time. Anthropology is an interdisciplinary subject, sometimes divided into ‘four fields’: cultural/social anthropology, physical anthropology, linguistic anthropology, and archaeology. This module will provide students with an overview of anthropology, with an especial focus on cultural/social anthropology. We will examine how kinship, gift exchange, and the household/home are understood in different societies and how they act to give shape to those societies. We will explore different ways of understanding the world and how to make comparisons between these, and ask what it means to think anthropologically.

LEARNING OUTCOMES

On completion of this module students should be able to:

1. Write an essay demonstrating awareness of key anthropological concepts
2. Demonstrate knowledge of some key anthropological facts
3. Demonstrate awareness of diversity of human cultures
4. Understand key features in the discipline of anthropology

SCHOOL OF ARCHAEOLOGY CULTURE

UCD School of Archaeology is committed to creating an environment where diversity is celebrated and everyone is treated fairly, regardless of gender, age, race, disability, ethnic origin, religion, sexual orientation, civil status, family status or membership of the travelling community. The School is also committed to the promotion of a study environment that upholds the dignity and respect of the individual and that supports every individual’s right to study in an environment free of any form of harassment, intimidation or bullying. For further information and supports, please visit <http://www.ucd.ie/archaeology/edi>

LECTURES AND TUTORIALS

This module is based around 10 lectures and five tutorials which provide the basis for reading and review of the relevant literature.

Lectures will be in person. It is essential that you attend/watch the lectures as these – and your reading—are the basis for the fortnightly multiple-choice-question (MCQ) quizzes, and also provide resources for your two major assessments.

Tutorials are an integral aspect of your module—they are designed to help you develop an in-depth and participatory engagement with anthropology, and help you complete your assessments. Tutorials are also a good way to meet new people in a smaller group setting! Tutorials will be held **every two weeks** (see timetable at back of handbook). You should **sign up for your tutorial** when you register for this module. Each tutorial will be no more than 45 minutes duration. All tutorials will ask you to do a small amount of preparatory work—normally reading a short article, watching a video or listening to a podcast. You will get much more out of the tutorial if you have done this first!

On weeks when you **do not** have your scheduled tutorials your tutors will be available for drop in queries in person. See Brightspace for details of these sessions and how to sign up. Your tutors are the people who mark your coursework, with a >25% sample—and normally about 40%—double marked by me to ensure consistency and standards. If you have queries about how to write the assignments, ask the tutors first!

The first week of teaching in the UCD spring trimester starts on Monday 23rd January. You will have your first tutorial and first lecture in this week, and the tutorial will come before the lecture. This is OK – we have designed the tutorial so you don't need to have attended the lecture first.

SUPPORTS

This handbook contains a list of lecture topics to help you view the structure of the module. Further support materials will be made available via Brightspace. **It is essential that you use Brightspace if you are a student on this module.**

There is a separate section on Brightspace for each lecture. I will provide a pre-lecture activity each week, usually something like a magazine article, podcast or video which will take 10-15 minutes. This is labelled '**Prepare**'. Please aim to do the 'Prepare' activity in advance of each week's lecture. The '**lecture**' section contains a **handout of the slides** to help you take notes - the slides alone will not give you all the information that you need! It also includes a **virtual version of the lecture**. For each lecture, a reading designed to deepen your knowledge of the lecture topic can also be found on Brightspace in the individual section for that lecture. This is labelled '**Consolidate**', and you are advised to read this after the lecture.

In addition to this module handbook, please ensure that you have a copy of the UCD School of Archaeology "**A Guide for Stage 1 Archaeology 2022–2023**" handbook (available via Brightspace). This contains important information on submission of coursework, grading, how to write an essay, etc. The handbook can be downloaded from Brightspace.

CONTACTING THE MODULE COORDINATOR

If you have any queries and would like to speak to me individually, my open office hours during Spring 2022 are on Wednesday from 10:00–11:00 AM and Thursday from 12:00–1:00 PM. For other times, please email me (jess.beck@ucd.ie) to arrange an appointment. You are also welcome to approach me before or after lectures. Alternatively, I am happy to deal with any queries you may have by email.

For tutor contact details, see Brightspace.

[For School Office role, details and contacts please click here >>](#)

TIMES

The module runs from 1:00 – 1:50 PM every Friday, for the first eleven weeks of term only. There is a bank holiday on Friday, April 7, so there will be no ARCH10150 lecture that day.

You will also have **one tutorial every fortnight** (weeks 1, 3, 5, 7, and 9) to reinforce and complement the lectures. Please ensure that you sign up for a tutorial.

MODULE OUTLINE

Week	Date	Lecturer	Topic
1 (UCD Week 20)	Jan 27	Beck	What is anthropology? Key concepts, key debates
2 (UCD Week 21)	Feb 3	Beck	Key themes: The story of human evolution
3 (UCD Week 22)	Feb 10	Beck	Key themes: The body
4 (UCD Week 23)	Feb 17	Beck	Key themes: Inequality
5 (UCD Week 24)	Feb 24	Warren	Key themes: Exchange
6 (UCD Week 25)	Mar 3	Warren	Key themes: Social organisation
7 (UCD Week 26)	Mar 10	Warren	Key themes: Hunter-gatherers
Two-week fieldwork/study period (March 11–26)			
8 (UCD Week 29)	Mar 31	Bruck	Key themes: Ritual and symbolism
Bank Holiday (April 7)			
10 (UCD Week 31)	Apr 14	Bruck	Key themes: Relationships and identity
11 (UCD Week 32)	Apr 21	Bruck	Key themes: House and home

Note: This is an indicative schedule and some detail and sequence may change

READINGS

The core readings for the course are all available as ebooks via UCD Library:

Eriksen T. (2015) *Small Places, Large Issues. An introduction to social and cultural anthropology (4th edition)*. London, Pluto Books ([ebook](#))

Eriksen, T. (2017) *What is Anthropology?* London, Pluto Press ([ebook](#))

Ingold T. (2018) *Anthropology: why it matters*. Cambridge, Polity ([ebook](#))

Hendry J., Underdown S. (2012) *Anthropology: A Beginner's Guide*. London, Oneworld ([ebook](#))

Further readings are available on Brightspace.

SUPPLEMENTAL READINGS

UCD library has e-access to two very useful Encyclopaedias, which contain many reviews of different aspects of anthropology. Please ensure to reference the individual sections correctly.

Wright, James D. (Eds) 2015 *International Encyclopedia of the Social & Behavioral Sciences (Second Edition)*, Oxford, Elsevier. [Sections on Anthropology](#).

Darity, WA. (Ed.) 2008 *International Encyclopedia of the Social Sciences*. 2nd ed., Macmillan Reference USA ([link](#))

Two recent short (& cheap!) paperbacks are really good, King's account of the early activities of his 'Renegade Anthropologists' is a brilliant read

Engelke, M. 2017 *Think Like an Anthropologist*. London. Penguin.

King, C. 2019 *The Reinvention of Humanity: How a Circle of Renegade Anthropologists Remade Race, Sex and Gender*. London. Vintage.

Finally, one longer but highly recommended book that combines archaeological and anthropological perspectives on human social flexibility is available at the library.

Graeber, D., & Wengrow, D. 2021. *The Dawn of Everything: A New History of Humanity*. London. Allen Lane.

ASSESSMENT

The assessment for this module comprises:

- 5 MCQs (worth 10% of your overall grade for the module)
- One piece of continuous assessment (a 750-word summary of a key theme in anthropology, worth 30% of your overall grade for the module). Full details will be available on Brightspace in due course.
- A 2000-word final essay (worth 60% of your overall grade for the module. Full details will be available on Brightspace in due course.

Graded work will be returned to you with feedback **four weeks after submission**.

ASSESSMENT TIMETABLE

	Assignment	%	Date Due
1.	MCQs	10%	A total of five MCQ quizzes will be held. One quiz will be set every two weeks, starting directly after the Week 2 lecture. Each quiz is completed online, via Brightspace and is open for one week. <i>i.e. MCQ on Weeks 1 & 2 opens at 2pm Fri 3rd Feb and closes at 1pm Fri 10th Feb 2023.</i>
2.	750-word summary	30%	On or before 3.00pm, Tuesday 28 th February—Week 6.
3	2000-word essay	60%	On or before 3.00pm, Tuesday April 25 th –Week 12.

ASSIGNMENT SUBMISSION

All assessments will be submitted digitally via Brightspace. Detailed information on how to submit your coursework and essay, and how to access your MCQ quizzes, will be available via Brightspace.

If you need to apply for a late submission of 14 days or less, please fill out and submit the [ARCH10150 Late Submission Request Form](#). If you need an extension of longer than two weeks, you will need to fill out a formal application for [extenuating circumstances](#).

- [For school coursework submission procedures please click here >>](#)
- [For Late Submission & extenuating circumstances procedures please click here >>](#)

FINAL COMMENT

Finally, we hope you enjoy the module and that it meets your expectations. Please remember that the more you engage with the module the more you will get out of it. If at any point you find yourself struggling, or simply want to discuss an issue further, please get in contact. The sooner we can identify issues the easier it will be to seek a resolution. Please note, you may also give formal anonymous feedback via the UCD feedback system—please do so for all your modules— we take it seriously and it helps us to continue to refine our approach.

INDICATIVE SCHEDULE (SPRING 2023)

Week	Date of Lecture	Tutorial?	Lecturer	Topic	Assessment
1	Jan 27 (UCD Week 20)	Y	Beck	What is anthropology? Key concepts, key debates	
2	Feb 3 (UCD Week 21)		Beck	Key themes: The story of human evolution	
3	Feb 10 (UCD Week 22)	Y	Beck	Key themes: The body	By Fri 10th Feb, complete MCQ Wk 1 & 2
4	Feb 17 (UCD Week 23)		Beck	Key themes: Inequality	
5	Feb 24 (UCD Week 24)	Y	Warren	Key themes: Exchange	By Fri, 24th Feb, complete MCQ Wk 3 & 4
6	Mar 3 (UCD Week 25)		Warren	Key themes: Social organisation	By Tues 28th Feb, First Assessment
7	Mar 10 (UCD Week 26)	Y	Warren	Key themes: Hunter-gatherers	By Fri, 10th Mar, complete MCQ Wk 5 & 6
Two-week fieldwork/study period (March 11–26)					
8	Mar 31 (UCD Week 29)		Bruck	Key themes: Ritual and symbolism	
9	Apr 7 (UCD Week 30)	Y*	X	No lecture (Bank Holiday, 7th April)	By Fri, 7th Apr, complete MCQ Wk 7 & 8
10	Apr 14 (UCD Week 31)		Bruck	Key themes: Relationships and identity	
11	Apr 21 (UCD Week 32)	Y	Bruck	Key themes: House and home	By Fri, 28th Apr, complete MCQ Wk 10 & 11
12	Apr 27 (UCD Week 33)			No lecture (after final essay)	By Tues 25th Apr, Final Essay

Note: This is an indicative schedule and some detail and sequence may change.

*Please note that during Week 9 (UCD Week 30) students registered for the Friday tutorial will need to take a tutorial earlier in the week to compensate for the UCD closure on Good Friday 07/04/23. We will advise you of alternative time slots in due course.